

IMPACT OF SKILLED LABOUR SHORTAGE ON BUILDING PROJECTS DELIVERY IN THE CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY IN ABUJA, NIGERIA

OKECHUKWU JOHN CHIMA

Department of Building Technology, Federal University of Technology, Minna
okeychima2002@gmail.com 08034451263

BABATUNDE ABDULRASHEED ISA

Department of Building Technology, Federal University of Technology, Minna
batunde@futminna.edu.ng 08102007785

ABSTRACTS

Skilled labour plays an important role in the ability of the construction industry to deliver on its mandate, - the provision of infrastructure. This study is aimed at assessing the current state of the construction industry's skilled workforce: prevalence of skilled labour shortage, causes and the impact of skilled labour shortage on building project delivery, with a view to providing solution. The study adopts a quantitative research approach using a Five-Likert scale structure questionnaire for the collection of data from Professionals and craftsmen in Abuja. The findings of the study indicated that skilled labour shortages exist in the industry. It further showed POP fixing, as the top trade experiencing skill shortage. The study identified sixteen factors causing skill shortage. The study showed that professionals ranked capacity-building related factors high, while craftsmen on the other hand have welfare related factors as top factors influencing skills shortage in construction industry. A simple linear regression between skill-shortage severity and building delivery success was conducted, and showed a coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.35$) which demonstrates that skill shortages account for about 35% of the variance in project delivery outcomes. Recommendations were made; increase investment in workshop, facility and practical training; provide standardized apprenticeship; and improve workers wage and welfare.

Keywords: Skill labour, Craftsmen, Construction Industry, Building delivery, Productivity, Impacts.

JEL Codes: J2; J3; O3.

1. INTRODUCTION

The construction industry is one of the most important industries in the world, and its strategic position in any nation's economy is never in doubt. According to Saka *et al.*, (2023), the construction industry makes a major contribution to gross domestic product (GDP) and is essential for infrastructure development, employment generation, and general economic expansion. Many countries' economic growth is largely dependent on the construction sector, which provides the framework for increasing urbanization, housing production, and infrastructure (Oni *et al.*, 2022). Umar (2023), opined that construction industry contributes about 50% percent of Nigerian government expenditure. Thus, shows that the construction industry is crucial in National development. Apart from contributing to GDP, this industry is responsible for construction of infrastructure such as roads, bridges, residential buildings, and industrial complexes that other industries depend on to run smoothly (Akomah *et al.*, 2020).

However, despite the importance of this sector, it has continued to struggle. One of the most critical challenges facing Nigeria's construction sector is the lack of workforce with the necessary skills to carry out the task required in the industry. Skilled labour in the construction sector, refers to people who have received specific training, knowledge, and experience that enable them to carry out difficult tasks effectively and safely (Brucker et al., 2021). This includes, heavy machinery operators, masons, carpenters, electricians, and plumbers, among others. For a building construction project to be successfully executed, skilled labour is one of the essential key factors that are required. It is believed that labour costs account for a sizeable portion (20%– 30%) of a project's actual cost (Karimi, 2018). This means that workforce productivity and abilities are very crucial in the success of construction projects. According to Orekan et al., (2020), the availability of adequate skilled workforce in the construction industry has long been established as not being adequately supplied. The Guardian newspaper of 14th July 2025, stated that the Nigeria's housing sector is facing a growing shortage of skilled artisans, bricklayers, plumbers, electricians, and carpenters which is threatening project timelines, inflating costs, and undermining quality across the building industry. The reason for this is not far-fetched, as past studies have highlighted some factors influencing skilled shortages in the industry, such as ageing workforce, as experienced workers are retiring and there are not enough young workers to replace them. This is attributed to the fact that young people are not interested in getting a job in construction. Another reason for the labor shortage is the difficulty of finding workers with the right and appropriate skills, occasioned by lack of formal apprenticeship system, and dearth of vocational and technical schools. The sector is therefore, struggling to achieve its objectives. This shortage of skilled labour does not occur without negative impacts on building project delivery. The effects include: project delays, higher labour costs; lower productivity; rework and, in certain situations; lowered standards for quality and safety; damage to reputation and client relations; and increased project costs (Karimi *et al.*, 2018; Bature *et al.*, 2025; Bala *et al.*, 2021; Oke *et al.*, 2020). The issue of skill labour availability is about both quality and quantity. Often time, the scarcity of labour is not just about the absence of labour, but, the availability of adequately trained craftsmen capable of filling vacant positions in the industry. Also, it has been noted that the stock of competent skilled construction workers has dwindled, and the industry which is expected to be the highest employer of labour after agriculture is populated with largely unskilled, inefficient and dissatisfied workers who see work in the industry as a stop-gap till “better things in the future.” Few actually see their crafts as careers worth investing in.

Furthermore, the industry's capacity to enhance project results and productivity is restricted by the lack of skilled personnel, which impedes the adoption and execution of novel construction technologies and inventive practices (Akomah *et al.*, 2020). A lack of trained workers in Nigeria's construction sector has serious economic consequences. A vibrant building industry is one of the main forces that drives economic expansion, job creation, and poverty reduction (Oni *et al.*, 2024). Particularly important in a nation with high unemployment rates is the sector's capacity to take on a sizable pool of young people without jobs. In addition to restricting employment prospects, the lack of qualified workers impacts the quality of infrastructure development, which is necessary to boost commerce, lower transportation costs, and enhance the general business environment (Saka and Olanipekun, 2023). Also, as noted by Oseghale *et al.*, (2015), insufficient infrastructure development reduces Nigeria's ability to compete on the international stage, thereby limiting economic influence of the country.

Previous study has been done in the past to address construction labor shortages in various contexts. For instance, Adagba *et al.* (2021) investigated factors affecting construction workers productivity in Zaria, Kaduna State. Kerai *et al.* (2023) assessed skilled labour shortage in the industry through the viewpoint of professionals. Oladiran and Onatayo (2019) investigated labor productivity in construction projects from the viewpoint of site managers, emphasizing key variables and management guidelines. Oseghale *et al.* (2015) explored the current state of the workforce, reasons for labor shortages, and their impacts on project delivery. Akomah *et al.* (2020) studied the skilled labor shortage in the building construction sector in the Central Region. However, not much of these studies assessed skills shortage from the perspective of professionals and craftsmen combined, which is important for identifying necessary solutions.

To address the perceived gap, promote sustainable development, and improve the overall state of skilled labour in the construction industry. Hence, the aim of this study is to evaluate the impacts of skills shortage on the construction industry, highlighting the prevalence and factors causing skilled labour shortage among selected trades. The skills considered in this study include the masonry/bricklaying, carpentry, plumbing, iron fixing, painting, tiling and pop fixing skills.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The construction industry is the backbone of many global economies, society and the environment and its core business evolves around engineering and buildings. In many countries, economic development is largely dependent on the construction sector, especially in developing nations like Nigeria. According to National Bureau of Statistics [NBS] (2024), approximately 9% of Nigeria's GDP comes from the construction sector. The sector is essential for infrastructure development, employment generation, and general economic expansion (Saka *et al.*, 2023). It is estimated that about, 100 million people are employed in the construction industry globally and it generates in excess of US\$10 trillion in annual revenue which translates to above 6% of the global GDP (WEF, 2018). The construction industry as a labour-intensive sector, rely on skilled labour to actualize the objectives. Labour, according to Oni *et al.* (2022), is a task that calls for the use of both the body and the mind. The work that goes into completing a certain task is considered labour. Labour force can be in form of unskilled, semi-skilled or skilled labour. A skill is an individual's ability to perform a productive task at certain level of competence (Echtelt, 2024). Wikipedia describes skilled labor as having the ability to operate autonomously, efficiently, and accurately. According to Elegbede and Akinbile (2024), typical characteristics of skilled worker include high salary and a high level of training or experience. The availability of skilled labour is one of the most critical factors for the effective functioning of the construction industry. The construction industry, despite the rapid technological innovations, still remains a hub of skills, because the complex nature of its activities can only be achieved by ready, willing, competent skilled force. Therefore, where qualified skilled craftsmen are involved, it tends to eliminate the concern of poor quality, low productivity, late project completion which often result to conflicts, cost and time overruns.

2.1. Theoretical Literature

Human Capital Theory provides the principal theoretical foundation for this study. The theory was developed by economists Gary Becker and Theodore Schultz in the 1960s to explain the role of education, training, and skills in improving labour productivity and economic performance. Applying the theory (Deming, 2022), posits that skills, knowledge, and health embodied in individuals represent a form of capital. Investment in this capital through formal education, apprenticeships, and on-the-job training yields returns in the form of higher productivity and

earnings. The shortage of skilled craftsmen and technicians in Abuja can be interpreted as a critical lack of investment in industry-specific human capital. Applying human capital theory will allow the study on skilled shortages to systematically analyze the link between the quality and quantity of the workforce (human capital stock) and its direct impact on construction project outcomes like timelines, cost, and quality (Bature *et al.*, 2025). It therefore moves the focus from a mere "labour shortage" to a deficit of valuable human capital, framing solutions around strategic investments in training and skill development.

Resource-Based View (RBV) of the firm (Barney, 2001) posits that a firm's superior performance can be achieved by developing tangible resources such as physical resources and financial resources and intangible assets such as skills and knowledge, company intellectual property such as patents or trademarks. Compared with tangible assets, intangible resources or capabilities such as skills and knowledge or human resource management practices can help firms to develop into competencies which are rare, valuable, and hard to imitate by competitors which lead to long term sustainable competitive advantage (Ding *et al.*, 2023). In the context of the construction industry, a stable, skilled, and productive workforce constitutes a key strategic resource. The current labour shortage in Abuja represents a failure to secure and retain this critical resource, directly undermining firms' competitive advantage and project delivery capabilities. The skilled workers are rare and valuable assets for construction firms, as the skills to complete tasks in different expertise areas or capabilities of using advanced technologies such as BIM, simulation or AI takes many years to develop on the worksites or via designed training programs to implement the technologies. Therefore, skills are considered as rare, valuable and difficult to be imitated by other competing firms. Utilizing RBV will guide the investigation to assess how construction firms in Abuja attempt to manage their human resources as strategic assets and how the scarcity of this resource affects their operational performance and long-term viability. It emphasizes that workforce strategy is integral to business strategy.

2.2. Empirical Literature

Empirical construction research typically measures skilled labour shortages indirectly using indicators such as: difficulties in recruiting qualified workers, high labour turnover, skill mismatches between job requirements and workforce abilities, and increased reliance on expatriate or informal labour. In Nigeria, multiple studies document persistent labour skill gaps, and the impacts on time, cost, quality of workmanship, safety, and sustainability. Uche and Akintoye (2016), in their study: "the economic effects of labour skill deficiencies on construction projects in Abuja", found that rework resulting from labour competence issues increased project costs by up to 18%. The study argued that the increase in cost as a result of rework was occasioned by the use of unskilled labours to construct projects.

Bature *et al.*, (2025) investigated the impact of of labour shortages and productivity in the construction industry in kaduna state. The study introduced Pearson Product-Moment Correlation (r) to examine if there was a statistically significant relationship between labour shortage and project performance. The study found strong positive relationship between severity of labour shortage and project performance with Correlation Coefficient ($r = 0.782$). As professionals' ratings for the severity of labour shortage causes increase, their ratings for the severity of project impacts also increase. The study thus concluded that there is a statistically significant, strong positive correlation between the perceived causes and impacts of labour shortages in the Kaduna construction industry. In addition, in a study, "the examination of the current state of the workforce, the reasons for labor shortages, and their effects on project delivery", by Oseghale *et al.*, (2015)

indicated that low pay, high labor mobility, and uncertain career trajectories are among the causes of labor shortages. The study further highlighted an ageing workforce, the poor admittance of younger workers into the construction industries, and employers' hesitation to invest in training, which leads to schedule disruptions and additional labor expenditures as factors that influence skilled shortage. Akomah *et al.*, (2020), investigated skilled labor shortages in the building construction business of the Central Region using a poll of project managers, site engineers, and foremen, found that there is shortage of skilled workers in the central region of Ghana. The study further showed that crafts like painting, decoration, electrical and tiling are the most affected by the skilled shortages. The causes of this deficiency were traced to economic relation, external forces, job preferences, job characteristics, job satisfaction, economic constraints and personal characteristics. Inadequate delivery and safety related issues were noted as the main impact of the shortage. To reduce the shortage of skilled workers, Akomah, suggested that workers should be supported and taught to develop the attitudes and skills required by their jobs.

Elegbede and Akinbile (2024), examined the perception of professionals on factors influencing skilled labor shortages in the Nigerian construction industry. The study involved 121 respondents from different professions in the industry. Using exploratory factor Analysis (EFA) and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA), the study identified and categorized these factors into groups based on their relation to each other. The findings showed the factors causing skilled shortage are grouped into: inefficiency of the government, stakeholders, and individuals; inadequate resources; the nature of construction works; technological changes; disorganized skilled labor markets; and unsatisfactory labor wages among others. The study further identified, a comprehensive strategy involving government policies, industry collaboration, education and training investment, workforce planning, competitive compensation, and the promotion of construction careers as essential strategies in tackling skilled shortages. Yusoff *et al.*, (2021) investigated the association between skilled workforce shortages and project performance in the construction industry. The findings revealed that project-related and human capital variables contribute to skilled labor shortages, which negatively impact construction project performance. The findings can assist industry players in better managing building projects by identifying and addressing skilled labor shortages. The shortage of skilled labour had been attributed to the growing number of ageing workforce; the lack of consistent training and training policies; the rise in projects; the negative public perception of construction workers; the unappealing nature of the industry to the majority of young people; limited government support for vocational training; economic instability; rural-urban migration; poor working conditions; skills mismatch; wage disparity and lack of job security. ((Bala *et al.*, 2021; Umeh & Ali, 2020; Oseghale *et al.*, 2015; Okoye & Ugochukwu, 2021; Adedeji & Fagbenle, 2023; Akintoye *et al.*, 2021; Obianagwa *et al.*, 2023; Taiwo & Mohammed, 2022)

The shortage of skilled labour impacts the industry in several ways which include: project delays, higher labour costs, lower productivity, lowered standards for quality and safety, cost overrun, enterprise failure, more rework, higher accidents rate, and increase in cost of production (Oke *et al.*, 2018; Oseghale *et al.*, 2015). The outcome of building project delivery depends on effective planning, execution, and control of work throughout the construction life cycle. According to Zuleta-Castellano *et al.*, (2023), effective management of a construction project hinges on the ability to monitor progress, identify potential issues and take timely corrective actions. This is important because, the success of a building project is not only determined by the completion of the project, but by how efficiently, safely, and sustainably it was delivered. To determine the success or otherwise of a building project, there are parameters that are employed. They include cost, schedule, quality, safety, client satisfaction and sustainability. These parameters and various

metrics play crucial roles in this process, providing projects managers with data needed to keep projects on track, within budget and desired quality. According to Simon (2019), without hard data, it is easy for construction projects to slip off course, and for problems like poor labour productivity, reworks, cash flow challenges or missed deadlines to spiral out of control.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study adopted quantitative research approach through in-depth understanding of the existing literature in the area of skills shortage. This allows for formulation of a clear research question for acquiring necessary information for the study. Two (2) forms of questionnaires (type-A and type-B) were designed and distributed. Questionnaire type-A was administered to professionals in the construction industry, operating in Abuja; while questionnaire type-B was administered to craftsmen in the sampled trades. The construction trades selected for this study were Masonry, Carpentering, Iron fixing, Plumbing, Painting, Tiling and Pop fixing. The choice of these trades is because they are the dominant trades in the building construction industry (Oseghale *et al.*, 2015). The population for this study is building construction firms in Abuja, that are registered with Industrial Training Fund (ITF). A total of 150 firms were identified and used as the sampling frame. Yamane formula cited in Owombo (2025), was applied to obtain a sample size of 125 firms, for questionnaire type A. For Questionnaire type-B, 15 craftsmen were selected from each of the sampled trades for equal representation, and this amounted to 105 craftsmen. Furthermore, Questionnaire type-A was administered to the managers and supervisors of construction firms, while Questionnaire type-B was administered to the craftsmen. Simple random and stratified sampling techniques were used to administer the questionnaires to professionals and craftsmen respectively. A total of 230 respondents were sampled. While a total of 164 valid responses which represent 71.3% were received and considered for analysis. Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential analysis, including simple regression, mean index score and standard deviation.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Demography of the Respondents

Responders' Data	Professionals		Craftsmen		
	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Frequency	Percentage (%)	
Profession			Crafts		
Architect	15	16.3	Masonry	13	18.1
Builder	30	32.6	Carpentry	11	15.3
Quantity Surveyor	12	13.0	Iron fixing	8	11.1
Engineer	25	27.2	Tiling	10	13.9
Estate Surveyor	10	10.9	Plumbing	10	13.9
			Painting	11	15.3
			Pop fixing	9	12.4
Total	92	100.0	Total	72	100.0
Years of Experience			Years of Experience		
0 - 5 years	5	5.4	0 – 5	2	2.8
6 – 10 years	35	38.1	6 – 10	13	18.1
11 – 15 years	23	25.0	11 – 15	22	30.6
16 – 20 years	16	17.4	16 – 20	20	27.8
21 years above	13	14.1	21 and above	15	20.8
Total	92	100.0	Total	72	100.0

Table 1 above represents the Professional qualifications, academic and years of experience of the respondents. This show that the respondents possess the required qualification in the industry to be able to participate effectively in this study.

Table 2: Respondents’ response to skill shortage in different trades

S/N	Skill Shortage in Different Trades	S.D	D	N	A	SA	N.R	T.S	MIS	Std.D.	RNK
		1	2	3	4	5					
1	POP Fixing	23	30	24	40	47	164	550	3.35	1.41	1 st
2	Iron Fixing	23	31	26	47	37	164	536	3.26	1.36	2 nd (tie)
3	Tiling	27	36	29	45	34	164	536	3.26	1.37	2 nd (tie)
4	Carpentry	28	34	24	42	36	164	516	3.14	1.41	3 rd
5	Painting	29	35	22	43	35	164	512	3.12	1.42	4 th
6	Masonry	24	37	29	44	30	164	511	3.11	1.34	5 th
7	Plumbing	26	37	29	40	32	164	507	3.09	1.36	6 th

Key: S.D. = Strongly Disagree, D = Disagree, N = Neutral, A.= Agree, SA. = Strongly Agree
 N.R = Number of Respondent, T.S = Total Score, MIS = Mean Item Score. RNK = Ranking,

Table 2 presents respondents’ perceptions of skill shortages across seven major building trades. POP fixing ranks highest (MIS = 3.35), indicating the most severe shortage. Iron fixing and tiling are jointly ranked second (MIS = 3.26). Carpentry (MIS = 3.14), painting (3.12), masonry (3.11), and plumbing (3.09) rank lower but still above the neutral point of 3.00, indicating general shortage across all categories. The consistency of the MIS values supports Yusoff et al., (2021), who found that multiple construction trades face simultaneous shortages due to low job attractiveness and unstable employment patterns.

Table 3: Professionals responses on factors causing skill shortages in building construction industry

S/N	Factors causing skill shortages in building construction industry	S.D	D	N	A	SA	N.R	T.S	MIS	Std.D.	RNK
		1	2	3	4	5					
1	Poor funding of technical and vocational schools	6	8	8	26	46	92	458	4.98	1.20	1 st
2	Absence of formal apprenticeship programme	4	8	9	32	39	92	452	4.95	1.18	2 nd
3	Ageing workforce	2	10	8	39	33	92	455	4.93	1.17	3 th
4	No defined professional pathway	4	9	9	26	44	92	454	4.91	1.16	4 th
5	Lack of interest by the youth	4	10	9	32	37	92	449	4.88	1.21	5 th
6	Low wages	5	5	8	46	28	92	446	4.85	1.19	6 th
7	Poor image of construction work	3	7	11	44	27	92	440	4.78	1.18	7 th
8	Poor government policy	5	9	11	32	35	92	433	4.70	1.15	8 th
9	Lack of job security	4	12	10	32	33	92	428	4.65	1.13	9 th
10	Changes in skills requirement	3	13	12	35	29	92	425	4.62	1.14	10 th
11	Economic changes	4	10	15	35	28	92	421	4.58	1.16	11 th
12	Get-rich-quick syndrome	5	10	11	44	22	92	427	4.64	1.17	12 th
13	New technology	5	11	13	39	24	92	424	4.61	1.13	13 th

S/N	Factors causing skill shortages in building construction industry	S.D	D	N	A	SA	N.R	T.S	MIS	Std.D.	RNK
		1	2	3	4	5					
14	Low motivation of workers	8	13	15	30	26	92	411	4.47	1.19	14 th
15	Hazardous nature of construction work	9	13	15	29	26	92	408	4.43	1.18	15 th
16	Growth of self-employment	7	19	14	28	24	92	400	4.35	1.15	16 th

Table 3 reveals a concentrated set of interrelated structural and economic factors driving skill shortages in the building construction industry. The highest-ranked factor, poor funding of training and vocational schools (MIS = 4.98), and absence of formal apprenticeship programme (MIS = 4.95) shows that lack of capacity building factors is seen by professionals in the industry as the top factors causing skills shortage. Ageing workforce made up the top three factors. This strongly supports the argument of Elegbede *et al.*, (2024) and Bala *et al.*, (2021), who note that inadequate investment in training infrastructure limits access to modern equipment, weakens pedagogy, and produces poorly skilled graduates. Akomah *et al.*, (2020) further contend that the chronic underfunding of technical education widens the gap between training output and industry skill requirements.

Table 4: Craftsmen response to factors causing skilled shortages in building construction industry

S/N	Factors causing skill shortages in building construction industry	SD	D	N	A	SA	N.R	T.S	MIS	Std.D.	RNK
		1	2	3	4	5					
1	Low wages	7	8	4	25	28	72	275	3.81	1.315	1 st
2	Low motivation of workers	4	12	8	20	28	72	272	3.77	1.271	2 nd
3	Lack of job security	2	10	15	25	20	72	267	3.70	1.098	3 rd
4	Ageing population of workers	6	13	5	22	26	72	265	3.68	1.343	4 th (tie)
5	Poor image of construction work	5	8	15	21	23	72	265	3.68	1.223	4 th (tie)
6	Absence of formal apprenticeship programme	5	12	12	20	23	72	260	3.65	1.275	5 th (tie)
7	Hazardous nature of construction work	4	10	14	23	21	72	263	3.65	1.192	5 th (tie)
8	Poor funding of TVET schools	6	9	14	23	20	72	258	3.58	1.244	6 th
9	Economic changes	6	12	12	20	22	72	256	3.55	1.301	7 th
10	No defined professional pathway	5	12	15	22	18	72	252	3.52	1.225	8 th
11	Lack of interest by the youth	7	13	10	19	23	72	254	3.50	1.355	9 th
12	New technology	5	12	14	25	16	72	251	3.48	1.202	10 th
13	Changes in skills requirement	7	12	13	21	19	72	249	3.45	1.301	11 th
14	Poor government policy	8	9	15	24	16	72	247	3.43	1.267	12 th
15	Get-rich-quick syndrome	8	10	15	22	17	72	246	3.41	1.288	13 th
16	Growth of self-employment	7	14	11	24	16	72	244	3.38	1.286	14 th

Table 4 highlights the unique perspective of craftsmen, whose proximity to daily project realities shapes their understanding of skill shortages. Unlike professionals, craftsmen place low wages

(MIS = 3.81) at the top, supporting Karimi *et al.*, (2018), who emphasizes that remuneration is central to artisans’ willingness to remain in construction. When wages fail to compensate for effort, risk, and time commitment, craftsmen increasingly shift to alternative sectors or informal self-employment. Closely following is low motivation of workers (MIS = 3.77), echoing Elegbede *et al.*, (2024), who explains that limited incentives, lack of recognition, and harsh site conditions diminish morale and reduce retention. The lack of job security (MIS = 3.70) also ranks highly among craftsmen and supports Taiwo & Mohammed (2022) argument that job security is an important factor for craftsmen in choosing skills. Craftsmen’s concern about the poor image of construction work (MIS = 3.68), which is tied on same point with ageing population of workforce, is consistent with Akomah *et al.*, (2020), who argue that negative societal perception of manual work discourages young people from entering the trades. Overall, craftsmen’s responses underscore a combination of poor incentives, unstable working conditions, declining training pathways, and demographic shifts.

The contrast in the responses is that, while professionals favoured capacity building related factors as the major causes of skills shortage in the industry, craftsmen choose workers’ welfare related factors as the major causes of skill shortages.

The Rate of Building Project Performance in the Building Construction Industry

The rate of performance of building project delivery is determined by the performance of some parameters (KPIs), including quality, cost, time, client satisfaction, safety, and the appropriateness of construction methods. Assessing these parameters provides insight into the performance level of construction activities and the extent to which industry practices align with project objectives.

Table 5: Professional response to success rate of building delivery performance in Abuja

S/N	Parameters	SD	D	N	A	SA	N.R	T.S	MIS	Std.D	RNK
		1	2	3	4	5					
1	Quality of workmanship	3	7	13	52	17	92	330	3.58	0.98	1 st
2	Cost performance	3	11	22	30	26	92	323	3.53	1.09	2 nd (tie)
3	Time performance	4	13	14	39	22	92	323	3.53	1.11	2 nd (tie)
4	Client satisfaction with project	5	10	8	30	39	92	325	3.52	1.29	3 rd
5	Safety measures on site	5	12	13	38	24	92	325	3.51	1.12	4 th
6	Use of adequate construction methods	6	8	17	22	39	92	322	3.50	1.29	5 th

Findings from Table 5 indicate that quality of workmanship ranked highest as the parameter that is mostly achieved by construction firms in building project delivery in Abuja (MIS = 3.58). reflect the findings of Windapo (2016) and Oni *et al.*, (2024), who highlight that skilled labour availability and competence strongly influence workmanship quality. The joint ranking of cost performance and time performance (MIS = 3.53) corresponds with Olawale *et al.*, (2023) and Hossein (2018) who emphasize cost control and time management as two critical pillars of project success, especially in environments with shifting labour competencies. Client satisfaction ranked 4th (MIS = 3.52). This is consistent with Karimi (2018), who argues that construction project success must ultimately be evaluated based on client expectations and perceived value. High client satisfaction reflects effective integration of cost, quality, and time outcomes. Safety measures (MIS = 3.51) followed, underscoring the fact that strong safety practices reduce accidents and ensure labour productivity. The recognition of adoption of adequate construction methods (MIS = 3.50) aligns with Adagba *et al.*, (2021), who argue that adopting appropriate construction techniques and

technology is essential for mitigating the negative effects of skill shortages. This indicates that project success is heavily dependent on both human and technical resources.

The Impacts of Skilled Labour Shortage on Building Project Delivery

The performance of building projects is heavily influenced by the availability and competence of skilled labor. Skilled labour shortages can disrupt timelines, affect quality, and compromise overall project delivery. To quantitatively assess this effect, a simple linear regression analysis was conducted to examine the relationship between skill-shortage severity and building delivery success in Abuja, Nigeria.

Table 6: Simple linear regression between skill-shortage severity and building delivery success in Abuja, Nigeria

Predictor (X)	B (Slope)	SE B	β_0 (Intercept)	R ²	F
Skill-shortage	0.106	0.084	3.032	0.35	1.59

B = Unstandardized coefficient, SE B = Standard error (approximate from variance of X and residuals), R² = coefficient of determination, F = F-statistic (approximate: t^2 for single predictor)

As shown in Table 6, the regression analysis reveals a medium positive relationship between skill shortages and project delivery success, with a slope (B) of 0.106. This indicates that an increase in the severity of skill shortages corresponds to only a marginal increase in the mean item score for project success. The coefficient of determination (R² = 0.35) demonstrates that skill shortages account for only 35% of the variance in project delivery outcomes, suggesting that other factors including project funding, project size, client expectations, technology adoption, and management practices when combined, have a more substantial impact. The F-statistic (F = 1.59) further highlights the limited predictive power of skill shortages when considered in isolation. These results imply that addressing skill shortages through training, apprenticeships, and vocational development is necessary but insufficient to ensure successful project delivery. This result support the existing literature asserting the relationship between skilled shortage severity and project performance (Bature et al., 2025), though with less significant impacts. Therefore, effective project outcomes require integrated strategies that combine workforce development with adequate remuneration, safety enforcement, stakeholder collaboration, and the adoption of modern construction methods.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study concludes that skilled labour shortages remain a significant but not exclusive challenge affecting building project delivery in Abuja construction industry. Critical trades such as POP fixing, iron fixing and tiling experience substantial skills deficits, driven by factors including poor funding of technical and vocational education, absence of structured apprenticeship, low wages, no defined professional pathways, an ageing workforce and lack of job security. The study further showed that, while the professionals in the industry highlighted capacity-building related factors as the major causes of skills shortage, craftsmen on the other hand believe that welfare related factors pose major threat to skills availability. The regression analysis (R = 0.35) confirms that skills shortages have impacts on the performance of building project delivery in Abuja. The findings underscore the need for comprehensive workforce development and stronger institutional frameworks to sustainably enhance construction project performance. The unavailability of necessary construction skills affects the success of project in terms of sustainability, quality, cost, time, health and safety as well as satisfaction of stakeholders.

There is need for training and absorbing of more skilled workforce in the construction industry, to enhance performance of construction projects. In view of this, construction firms and stakeholders

both public and private sectors should invest in training, research and developing their employees cutting across various departments of the organization. There is also a need for government agencies such as Industrial Training Fund (ITF) to do more in terms of providing training centres, and introducing youths to construction related disciplines at early stages of their education. The Ministry of labour and productivity and stakeholders in the industry should ensure significant improvement on the welfare of craftsmen, including wages, job security, career progression, to be able to attract and retain skilled workers in the industry.

REFERENCE

- Adagba, T., Ati, J.O., & Makarfi, A.I. (2021). An assessment of labour productivity influencing factors in the construction industry: A case study of Zaria, Nigeria. *Journal of Civil Engineering Frontiers* 2(2):26-37.
- Adedeji, Y. M. D., & Fagbenle, O. I. (2023). Inflation and labour cost dynamics in the Nigerian construction industry. *Journal of Construction in Developing Countries*, 28(1), 45-60.
- Akintoye, A., Oyedele, L. O., & Bilau, A. A. (2021). Labour shortages in the construction industry: A review of causes and mitigation strategies. *International Journal of Construction Management*, 21(6), 553-567
- Akomah, B. B., Ahinaquah, L. K., & Mustapha, Z. (2020). Skilled labour shortage in the building construction industry within the central region. *Baltic journal of real estate economics and construction management*, 8(1), 83-92
- Amrop, L. (2018). Developing Skills to Meet Infrastructure Demand. *Infrastructure Sector Research Report*
- Bala, K., Lawal, I., & Musa, A. (2021). An analysis of labour productivity in construction projects in Northern Nigeria. *Journal of Construction Economics and Management*, 13(2), 145-161
- Bature, J. K., Bareh, Y. G., Buba, G. S & Bako, E. D. Investigating the Impact of Labour Shortages and Productivity in the Construction Industry in Kaduna State. *Journal of Environmental Management & Construction Research* 10(4)
- Barney, J. B. (2001). Is the resource-based “view” a useful perspective for strategic management research? Yes. *Academy of Management Review*, 26(1), 41–56. doi:10.5465/AMR.2001.4011938.
- Brucker, J. B., Galic, M., & Marenjak, S. (2021). *Review of the Construction Labour Demand and Shortages in the EU. Buildings*, 11(1), 17
- Deming, D. J. (2022). Four facts about human capital. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 36(3), 75– 102. <https://doi.org/10.1257/jep.36.3.75>
- Ding, M. J., Jie F., Sisombat, S. and Bandlamudi, B. S. (2023). Impact of the Skill Shortage on the Construction Supply Chain Performance in Australia. *Civil Engineering Journal* 9(2) 356-371.
- Echtelt, R.V. <https://www.ag5.com/what/are/skills?>
- Elegbede, O. T., and Akinbile, B. F. (2024). Perception of professionals on factors influencing skilled labor shortages in the Nigerian construction industry. *Journal of Civil Engineering and Construction Technology*. 14(1),1-16.
- Hossein, K., Dadi, G. B., Goodrum, P. and Srinivasan, C. (2018). Impact of skilled labour availability on construction project cost performance. *Journal of Construction Engineering and Management*, 144(7)

- Karimi H., Taylor T. R. B., Goodrum P. M. (2018). Analysis of the impact of craft labour availability on North American construction project productivity and schedule performance. *Journal of Construction Management and Economics*, 35(6)
- Kerai, V., Solanki, S.V., & Patel, A.S. (2023). Skill Labour Shortage in Construction Industry *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts (IJCRT) 11(2)*, 2320-2882.
- Mkhonza, L. and Letsoalo-Fuze, A. (2017). Understanding the Hard to Fill Vacancies in the Public Service Sector: The Case of Provincial Departments. *Public Service Sector Education and Training Authority (PSETA 2017)*
- Muhwezi, L., Acai J. and Otim G. (2014). An Assessment of the Factors Causing Delays on Building Projects in Uganda. *International Journal of Construction Management 3(1)*:13-23
- National Bureau of Statistics (NBS). (2024). *Nigeria's GDP and the contribution of the construction sector*. National Bureau of Statistics.
- Obianagwa, C. E., Ifem, L. A., Udeani, N. Ugwuozor, S. F., Nte, E. O. and Eze, N. C. (2023). Poor funding of Research and Development: An Achilles Heel to Technological Growth in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Allied Research 8(4)*:27-44.
- Oke, A., Aigbavboa, C. and Khangale, T. (2018). *Effect of Skills Shortage on Sustainable Construction*. Springer International Publishing AG.
- Oke, A. E., Aigbavboa, C. O., & Oyedele, L. O. (2020). Determinants of labour productivity in the Nigerian construction industry. *Journal of Engineering, Design and Technology, 18(5)*, 1057-1075.
- Okoye, P., & Ugochukwu, S. (2021). Enhancing productivity in Nigeria's construction industry: A study of labour management practices. *Journal of Construction Management and Economics, 6(1)*, 23-31.
- Oladiran O, Onatayo D (2019). Labour productivity: Perception of site managers on building projects. *LAUTECH Journal of Civil and Environmental Studies 2(1)*:1-10
- Olawale, S. and Sun, Y. (2023). Critical factors affecting construction project delivery in Nigeria. *Journal of Construction Economics, 31(1)*, 42–59.
- Oni, O. Z., Olanrewaju, A., Khor, S. C., and Akinbile, B. F. (2022). A comparative analysis of construction workers' mental health before and during COVID-19 pandemic in Nigeria. *Frontiers in engineering and built environment, 3(1)*, 63-75.
- Oni, O., Ogunbayo, B., Ogunlope, K., Aigbavboa, C., & Akinbile, B. (2024). Construction Skilled Labor Adequacy and its Impact on Nigeria Economy. In International Conference on Construction in the 21st Century (CITC 2024), Rio de Janeiro, Brazil.
- Orekan, A. A. and Babatunde, O. (2020). Evaluation of the Impact of Building Artisans on Residential Housing Delivery in Mupin Town, Ado-Odo/Ota Local Government, Ogun State.
- Oseghale, B. O., Abiola-Falemu, J. O., & Oseghale, G. E. (2015). An Evaluation of Skilled Labour shortage in selected construction firms in Edo state, Nigeria. *American Journal of Engineering Research, 4(1)*, 156-167.
- Owombo, P.T. (2025). Effect of Lagos State Covid-19 Action Recovery Economic Stimulus on Welfare of Arable Crop Farmers in Ikorodu, Lagos State. *Journal of Economics and Allied Research 10(4)*:35-43.
- Saka, N., and Olanipekun, A. O. (2023). Relationship between the economy, construction sector and imports in Nigeria. *International Journal of Construction Management, 23(2)*, 297-306.
- Simon, A. A. (2019). A case study of performance analysis of design-build and integrated project methods. *International Journal of Construction Education and Research 17(1)*.

- Taiwo, T., & Mohammed, I. (2022). Rural-urban migration and its implications on labor availability in Kaduna State's construction sector. *Journal of Urban Development and Planning*, 24(1), 78-93.
- Uche, O. & Akintoye, A. (2016). The economic effects of labour skill deficiencies on construction projects in Abuja. *Journal of Construction Economics*, 26(1), 45–62.
- Umar, A. S. (2023). *Assessment of Skills and Competencies Offered by Built Environment Graduates in Construction Firms in Abuja* (Doctoral dissertation).
- Umeh, O. A., & Ali, A. S. (2020). Working conditions and labour turnover in the Nigerian construction industry. *Journal of Construction in Developing Countries*, 25(2), 175-193.
- WEF & BCG, (2018). *Shaping the Future of Construction: An Action Plan to Solve the Industry's Talent Gap*. WEF
- Windapo, A. O. (2016). Skilled labour supply in the South African construction industry: The nexus between certification, quality of work output and shortages. *SA Journal of Human Resource Management*, 14(1), 1–8.
- <https://guardian.ng/property/in-search-of-workforce-for-housing-lagging-construction-sites>.
- Yusoff, N. S. M., Rahim, F. A. M. and Chuing, L. S. (2021). The relationship of skilled labour shortages and project performance in construction industry: A conceptual framework. *Journal of Project Management Practice (JPMP)*, 1(1), 1-21.
- Zuleta-Castellano, H.R., Sanabria-Ospino, A.E., Puerta-Guardo, F.A., Ramirez-Garcia, J.C and Fajardo-Moreno, W.S. (2023). Performance management in construction projects: a systematic literature review. *Revista DYNA*, 90(228), 55-65.